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**Title: SOP for Preparation of Vanquish Neo UHPLC-TSQ
Altis Plus for analysis**

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Summary

The Thermo Scientific™ Vanquish Neo UHPLC coupled with TSQ Altis Plus provides high sensitivity, selectivity and robustness and is ideal for LC-MS workflows from discovery research with limited sample amounts to high-throughput validation in large sample cohorts. This SOP describes the preparation for analysis and daily maintenance of Vanquish Neo UHPLC-TSQ Altis Plus QqQ, preparation of mobile phases and wash solvents and preparation of the sequence. Calibration of TSQ Altis Plus is described in *SOP for System Calibration and System Check Routine of Altis QqQ*.

Equipment

- 10 µL, 200 µL, and 1000 µL pipette
- Mini vortex

Consumables & glassware

- 10 µL, 100 µL, 200 µL, and 1000 µL tips
- 250 µL polypropylen vials with screw lid
- 100 ml and 500 ml graduated cylinders

Reagents

- Acetonitrile (ACN) in LC-MS grade, formic acid (FA) in LC-MS grade, milliQ water, isopropanol in LC-MS grade

Preparation of mobile phases and wash solvents

- **Mobile phase A = 0.1% FA**
 - Mix 100 ml of MiliQ water with 100 μ L of FA in LC-MS grade.
- **Mobile phase B = 100% ACN with 0.1% FA**
 - Mix 100 ml of ACN in LC-MS grade with 100 μ L of FA in LC-MS grade.
- **Strong wash = 80% ACN with 0.1% FA**
 - Mix 800 ml of ACN in LC-MS grade with 200 ml of MiliQ water and 1 ml of FA in LC-MS grade.
- **Weak wash = 0.1% FA**
 - Mix 1000 ml of MiliQ water with 1 mL of FA in LC-MS grade.
- **Seal wash = 75% IPA with 0.1% FA**
 - Mix 750 ml of IPA in LC-MS grade with 250 ml of MiliQ water and 1 ml of FA in LC-MS grade.

Preparation of system suitability check material

- **QC standard peptide mix**
 - Mix 14 native standard peptides (Table 1) to final concentration 1.3 μ M, vortex properly and store aliquots in freezer at -20 °C.
 - For testing the system before and during analysis, thaw prepared aliquot of QC standard peptide mix, vortex properly and dilute 10x with 5% ACN with 0.1% FA to final concentration of each standard peptides 130 nM.

Table 1: Peptides used in QC standard peptide mix

Accession Number	Gene Name	Protein Name	Peptide sequence
PODJI8	SAA1	Serum amyloid A1	FFGHGAEDSLADQAANEWGR
PODJI8/PODJI9	SAA1/2	Serum amyloid A1 and A2	SFFSFLGEAFDGR EANYIGSDK
PODJI9-1	SAA2	Serum amyloid A2 Isoform 1	GAEDSLADQAANK LTGHGAEDSLADQAANK GPGGAWAAEVISNAR
P35542	SAA4	Serum amyloid A4	FRPDGLPK EALQGVGDMGR
P02763	ORM1	Alpha-1-acid glycoprotein 1	NWGLSVYADKPETTK
P19652	ORM2	Alpha-1-acid glycoprotein 2	SDVMYTDWK TLMFGSYLDDEK
P01009	SERPINA1	Alpha-1-antitrypsin	AVTIDEK SVLLGQLGITK
P02741	CRP	C-reactive protein	ESDTSYVSLK

- **QC pool of digested serum/plasma**

- 8 replicates of serum/plasma were prepared according to *SOP for Quantification of inflammatory proteins in serum/plasma using UHPLC/SRM-MS*.
- Replicates were dissolved in 40 μ L of 5% ACN with 0.1% FA (step 22 in the *SOP for Quantification of inflammatory proteins in serum/plasma using UHPLC/SRM-MS*) and pooled.
- 20 μ L aliquots of pool of digested serum/plasma were stored in -20 °C.
- For testing the system before and during analysis, thaw QC pool of digested serum or plasma (according to the sample matrix you are going to analyze) and vortex properly.

Preparation of Vanquish Neo – TSQ Altis Plus for analysis

1. Exchange the mobile phases (change the mobile phases every week).
2. Run script **B01 Change Liquids/Solvents** from Script Panel in the Vanquish User Interface (Figure 1). Activate the type of the bottle you exchanged and “Refresh only” option if you exchanged a solvent bottle for the same solvent type.

Figure 1: Script Panel in the Vanquish User Interface

3. Check solvents for needle rinsing (strong and weak wash) and refill if necessary.
NOTE: If the wash bottle is exchanged or refilled, run script **B01 Change Liquids/Solvents** as described previously.
4. Check solvent for seals rinsing (seal wash) and refill if necessary.
NOTE: If the wash bottle is exchanged or refilled, run script **B01 Change Liquids/Solvents** as described previously.
5. Empty the waste reservoir under the instrument.
6. Run script **B03 Clean Up System**.
7. Run diagnostic script **D01 Test System Back Pressure** to test the system for blockages.

8. If the diagnostic script D01 identifies increased backpressure of the needle seat, perform script **C21 Clean or Replace Needle Unit and Seat**, select **Clean needle seat** and proceed according to the instructions in the script
NOTE: It may need to be executed multiple times to recover the needle seat from the blockage. If the cleaning procedures are unsuccessful, proceed to replace the needle seat according to the script.
9. Check Instrument blank (5% ACN with 0.1% FA) in the autosampler and refill or exchange the vial if necessary.
10. Place QC standard peptide mix for system suitability check to the autosampler.
11. Place QC pool of digested serum or plasma (according to the sample matrix you are going to analyze) to the autosampler.
12. Connect the column.
13. In the **Vanquish Neo** window in Chromeleon, check if the Vanquish Neo is connected and in Idle status and turn on the flow (1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, 5% of Solvent B; Figure 2).

Figure 2: Vanquish Neo in Idle status with flow on

14. In the **Thermo MS Tuning** window, turn the System on (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Turning TSQ Altis Plus system on

15. In the **Thermo MS Tuning** window, check spray stability – click the Plot Chromatogram icon at the lower right of the window (Figure 4A) -> in the Plot Chromatogram dialog window activate Spray stability and TIC (Figure 4B) -> click OK

NOTE: The Signal stability RSD should be < 10%. Wait at least 40-50 scans to evaluate the stability (Figure 4C).

Figure 4: Check of the spray stability. A – Plot Chromatogram icon, B – Plot chromatogram dialog window with settings, C – Stability signal plot

16. Prepare sequence according to following setup:

- I. Instrument blank (5% ACN with 0.1% FA)
- II. Instrument blank
- III. System suitability check (QC standard peptide mix)
- IV. QC pool of digested serum/plasma
- V. Instrument blank
- VI. Samples 1-3
- VII. Instrument blank
- VIII. Sample 4-6
- IX. Instrument blank
- X. Sample 7-9 ...

NOTE: Measure Instrument blank after every 3 samples

NOTE: Measure QC pool of digested serum/plasma with every 30 samples.

XI. End with Instrument blank, QC pool of digested serum/plasma and 2x Instrument blank.

17. Start LC-QQQ analysis.

NOTE: If there are problems and the sequence is interrupted, run script **B03 Clean Up System** and diagnostic scripts **D01 Test System Back Pressure** and **D02 Test System tightness** to localize the problem. Cap/seal samples and store at -20 °C whilst troubleshooting.

18. Check the initial blanks and QCs.

19. When the LC-QQQ sequence is finished, run script **B03 Clean Up System** and script **D01 Test System Back Pressure**.

20. Store the samples at -20 °C.